
Balancing Innovation and Living Experience: The Role and Limits of Modern Technological Approaches to Anatomy Education across Disciplines

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ABSTRACT: Human anatomy, the study of the human body's structure, is the foundation of health and medical sciences. Over time, its exploration has expanded beyond medicine, finding applications in diverse fields such as therapy, creative and performing arts, kinesiology, and engineering. Despite the widespread use of anatomical knowledge across diverse disciplines, there is a significant knowledge gap in that these various disciplines do not learn educational methods from one another; there is thus a great (and as-yet unexplored) opportunity for interdisciplinary learning and innovation. This narrative review explores the trending methods of instruction in anatomy education across disciplines, focusing on the application, successes, and limitations of modern technological tools – including 3D visualization systems, virtual and augmented reality (VR & AR), advanced imaging modalities, and 3D printing. This review also critically examines how state-of-the-art technology commonly overshadows living anatomy, where our own bodies are the original instructional tool of anatomical education. By integrating insights from multiple disciplines, this narrative review offers insight on how living anatomy can complement the innovative technological advancements, and why it would manifest as a balanced, holistic approach to teaching and learning human anatomy.

INTRODUCTION

Human anatomy, the study of the human body's structure, is the foundation of health and medical sciences (Duffin, 2021). Although rooted in medicine for many hundreds of years (Duffin, 2021; Singh et al., 2015), its development and application has transcended disciplinary boundaries, finding applications in therapy, creative and performing arts, kinesiology, and engineering. Although similar anatomical concepts are emphasized across these disciplines, their methods of instruction can differ significantly as they are dedicated to the unique goals of each field. There is a notable knowledge gap in that these various disciplines do not share educational methods and curricula with one another; there is thus a great (and as-yet unexplored) opportunity for interdisciplinary learning and collaboration in human anatomical education.

This narrative review summarizes curriculum insights from multiple disciplines, exploring each discipline's preferred methods of instruction in anatomy education. With a focus on modern technological tools— including 3D visualization software, virtual and augmented reality (VR & AR), advanced imaging modalities, and 3D printing, this paper offers a broader perspective on the current application, successes, and limitations of such tools in anatomy education across disciplines. This review further stresses the enduring relevance of living anatomy – anatomy learned through experiencing one's own body in real-time – and how it may supplement the limitations of innovative technology to offer a balanced and holistic anatomy curriculum. By blending technology with living anatomy, educators have an opportunity to create a comprehensive and balanced anatomy curriculum that prepares students for real-world demands.

This narrative review is particularly relevant for anatomy educators who want to improve their teaching by learning from the masters of different disciplines, for those exploring how a strong anatomical foundation can be beneficial to all fields, and for those aiming to incorporate more technological teaching approaches.

The scope of this paper will focus on human gross anatomy education as it is most commonly taught across multiple disciplines.

METHODS

This review draws upon a wide range of literature, including recent studies, reviews, and educational reports, to synthesize current trends in innovative anatomy education. The keywords searched across PubMed and Scopus included "anatomy education", "3D visualization", "medical imaging", "virtual reality", "augmented reality", "3D printing", in addition to discipline-specific terms like "therapy", "visual arts", "dance", "kinesiology", "engineering". Titles and abstracts were screened for relevance, followed by full-

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text review of selected studies. A total of 7646 abstracts were considered for inclusion, with 59 (0.8%) papers being selected for inclusion in this review. See PRISMA flow chart

Inclusion criteria required the studies explore the use of technological tools anatomy education in at least one discipline, published within the last 20 years, and written in English. Studies pertaining to North American post-secondary institutions were prioritized. Further sources, such as curricula, program structures, and syllabi were identified through specific programs in North American institutions' websites.

BACKGROUND

Modern Technology's Influence on Didactic Lectures and Anatomical Dissections

Formal lectures have been key to anatomical education since before Ancient Greek (200 AD to 1700 AD) and they are still the dominating instructional methods today (Anyanwu, 2014; Estai & Blunt 2016; Siwela & Mawera, 2017). Lectures effectively disseminate large amounts of information, such as anatomical foundation and vocabulary, to a large audience at the lowest cost (Siwela & Mawera, 2017). Cadaver dissections have been present since Ancient Egypt (3100 BC). Present day dissections actively prepare students for clinical practice through team building, problem solving, self-directed learning, encounters with death, and develops manual skills to understand the relationship between structure, function, symptom, and pathology (Estai & Blunt, 2016; McBride & Drake, 2020; Parker, 2002).

Today's anatomy education, however, is confronting increased class sizes and costs of dissections. There is a global trend of anatomy educators favoring more technologically advanced approaches to enhance lectures. While this review primarily explores the use of modern technological tools, it is important to recognize the foundational role of cadaveric dissections in anatomy education. Cadaver-based learning has long provided tactile experiences and direct interaction with human tissues and anatomical variation (Bolino et al., 2023). The virtual and digital tools to be explored in this review are created from data gathered from human

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cadaveric material (Bartoletti-Stella et al., 2021). Therefore, we acknowledge the profound contribution of individuals who donate their bodies to scientific research, without whom these advancements would not be possible (Iwanaga et al., 2021).

Anatomy education plays a crucial role in many disciplinary and professional programs. Physiotherapists and occupational therapists, for example, rely on their anatomical comprehension to improve a patient's ability to move their body and to perform daily activities. With their thorough understanding of musculoskeletal anatomy, they identify injury or dysfunction and prescribe targeted interventions or equipment to restore optimal movement and function (Cramer et al., 2005). Many North American therapy programs teach anatomy through lectures over one or two semesters within the first year, allowing students to select more specialized physical science courses later, including courses that offer cadaver dissections (Kurul et al., 2020; Milian et al., 2024; University of Toronto, 2024).

There is a symbiotic and inseparable bond between art and anatomy as well. Visual arts students benefit greatly from studying anatomy, learning predominantly from observing the human body's structure, proportions, and movement of a live figure drawing model (known as life drawing). Anatomical comprehension enhances artistic realism and expressiveness in their work (Kermanian et al., 2023), therefore anatomy lessons or lectures are typically intertwined within life drawing classes (Inalouei, 2024). Dancers predominantly learn musculoskeletal anatomy through living anatomy in dance class, where experience, experimentation, and proprioception of movement develop a profound understanding of the structure and function of their bodies (Denichaud, 2024). A dancer's thorough understanding of how to move their bodies enables them to optimize performance in their genre of dance, prevent injury, and refine their technique for full expressions of complex movements (Rózsavölgyi 2021; Smith 2019).

Kinesiology students learn the peculiarities of our locomotor apparatus that are essential to understanding body structure, movements, responses and adaptations to physical exercise. This is essential for optimizing athletic performance, preventing injuries, and enhancing rehabilitation strategies (Viana et al., 2019). Kinesiology students use traditional textbook readings and lectures for theoretical education and cadaver laboratory sessions for practical applications of joint mechanics, biomechanical principles, movements, and the physiological responses of the body during exercise (Catena & Carbonneau, 2019; Downie & Burke 2023; Enoka & Duchateau, 2016). North American undergraduate kinesiology programs typically begin anatomy education within the first two semesters, then require more advanced anatomy courses across the four years of the program (University of Toronto, 2024; University of Waterloo, 2024).

Bioengineering combines anatomy, engineering, biomaterials science, cell biology, and medicine to create technological advancements aimed at enhancing human health (Bisht et al., 2019). This includes artificial organs, prosthetics, and drug delivery systems. Undergraduate bioengineering students in North America typically take one or two anatomy courses, with lectures often integrated into broader biomedical engineering classes such as biomechanics or biomedical systems. The emphasis on anatomy varies by institution, where some programs consider anatomy an elective (Guelph University, 2024) while others incorporate medical lectures and gross anatomy laboratory sessions to improve anatomical quiz performance, reduce anxiety, and increase appreciation, motivation, and direct application to research projects (Topping et al., 2018; University of Florida, 2023). Bioengineering programs teach anatomy through practical experiences, expert demonstrations, active learning activities, and long-term follow-up assessments (Singh et al., 2019).

Anatomy education thus serves as a foundational component across therapy, visual arts, dance, kinesiology, and bioengineering. Each field prioritizes certain anatomical concepts and instructional tools to meet its unique demands, whether guiding therapists in patient care, enhancing artistic realism for visual artists, supporting dancers' movement awareness and injury prevention, or propelling bioengineers to enhance quality of life. While the depth and delivery of anatomical education varies, the goal in each discipline is to build a comprehensive understanding of the human structure and function that aligns with the practical needs of each discipline. This broad integration of anatomy highlights its enduring relevance and underscores the opportunities for cross-disciplinary collaboration.

As anatomy education progresses, modern technologies increasingly supplement traditional lectures and dissection to address challenges like larger class sizes and limited cadaver access. The following section explores the results of this narrative review, how technological approaches are used across disciplines.

RESULTS OF NARRATIVE REVIEW: INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACHES ACROSS DISCIPLINES

With anatomy education expanded across multiple disciplines, this section summarizes the innovative technological instructional methods such as computer-based 3D visualization software, virtual reality (VR) & augmented reality (AR), medical imaging, and 3D printing, and how they enhance comprehension in their specific disciplinary context.

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3D VISUALIZATION SOFTWARE

3D visualization software is a type of computer-based learning (CBL) that showcases complex structures from multiple angles. In anatomy education, 3D visualization guarantees better understanding of fine anatomical details in comparison to 2D images (Bertolini et al., 2021). Therapy students immensely benefit from 3D visualization methods that link theory with practice, facilitating long-term comprehension of complex anatomical concepts (Rezayi et al., 2022; Trelease, 2015). Linking theory from lectures with clinical practice in CBL has shown to develop critical thinking skills, clinical reasoning abilities, and provides therapy students the context of their future roles as healthcare professionals (Bergman et al., 2011; Estai & Bunt, 2016; Padulo et al., 2016). Visual arts students learn the foundations of the human body's structure, proportions, and movement to aid in creating realistic and expressive artwork. Today, many art classes offer anatomy classes with live models, anatomy books, and digital resources. CBL programs like ZBrush, 3D Anatomy for Artists, and BodyViz showcase 3D anatomy for interactive exploration of the human form (Inalouei, 2024). Some dancers are fortunate enough to experience anatomical visualization software and motion capture systems to analyze and precisely refine movements (Tsampounaris et al., 2016). However, dance education mostly uses one's own living, experiential anatomy to foster deep understandings of the body's interconnectedness and functionality (Smith 2019). Bioengineering programs have varying emphasis on anatomy education. The bioengineering program of Newcastle University integrated anatomical lectures on joint replacement and biotribology (synovial joints and their artificial replacement). Students learned joint anatomy through a series of practical activities involving 3D anatomical software (Primal Pictures), models of human joints, and critiques of specific joint designs. Students submitted 3000-word projects on the in-depth analysis of joint anatomy and showed a substantial comprehension of joint anatomy based on the lectures (Joyce 2012).

VIRTUAL REALITY (VR) AND AUGMENTED REALITY (AR)

Immersive VR consists of a virtual world, immersion, sensory feedback, and interactivity (Kurul et al., 2020; Sherman & Craig, 2019; Sinou et al., 2023). With either head-mounted devices or rooms that cover the user's 360-degree field of view, it provides an experience that completely isolates the individual from the external environment (Laver et al., 2017). These programs allow practical understanding through visualization and manipulation of 3D anatomical structures (Khot et al., 2013; Zhao et al., 2020). Dissection VR is popular in medical anatomy education as it mimics real dissection through multi-angled visualizations and interactions with simulated objects in this artificial 3D space (Estai & Blunt, 2016). It is also less expensive compared to real dissections and can be helpful for students with low spatial ability (Kurul et al., 2020). In fact, Zhao et al. (2020)'s meta-analysis found VR more effective than 2D methods when it comes to spatial anatomy comprehension. Zhao also found higher scores in learning satisfaction when VR learning tactics were employed.

Augmented reality (AR) combines 3D virtual content with real-world environments to display complex and difficult-to-show anatomical structures, allowing users to interact with both virtual and real environment (Estai & Blunt 2016; Jamali et al., 2015; Kurul et al., 2020). There are inconsistent findings on the efficacy of AR, for example, Bork et al. (2019) found minimal improvement in radiology anatomy test scores between students using AR versus traditional 2D atlases while Henssen et al., (2020) found a 10.6% improvement in test scores from students using a tablet-based AR. It is inconclusive if AR significantly impacts learning outcomes and spatial abilities. Furthermore, the average cost of immersive VR hardware and 1-year software license is \$4,900 USD. For comparison, the average cost of a single cadaver laboratory is \$1,268.20 per resident (Crockatt et al., 2023).

VR systems are coveted in therapeutic and diagnostic fields due to their engagement, multiple perspectives, self-directed learning, and customizable learning experiences for clinical experience, such as complex anatomical processes and pathologies (Azuma et al., 2001). Kurul et al. (2020) investigated the effect of VR on anatomy education in 72 randomized undergraduate physical therapy students. They found that VR's pre-test and post-test results (107% increase) were significantly higher than the control group's (26% increase). Most students had positive perceptions on VR sessions, verbally expressing high rates of enjoyment and effectiveness in studying anatomy structures. High rates of enjoyment can be essential in self-directed learning. In a study by Telner et al. (2010), 90.5% of participants agreed or strongly agreed with the statement, "I learn more when I have fun", supporting the accomplishments and the positives of the VR group.

Kinesiology scholars have consistently advocated for active learning approaches over traditional lectures, citing better learning outcomes (Knudson, 2019; Knudson & Wallace, 2019). VR and AR technology holds significant promise in enhancing anatomy student engagement of biomechanical concepts through immersive experiences showcasing the body and real-time changes during human movement (Keogh et al., 2024). Meyer et al. (2021) integrated Anatomage Table, a virtual 3D dissection program into undergraduate and graduate kinesiology anatomy classes. Virtual dissection activities are a cost-effective way for kinesiology students to actively explore anatomical structures and their 3D relationships in a stimulating learning environment. Students learned authentically rather than simply memorizing isolated facts about origins and insertions of muscles. For example, rather than simply listing muscles, origins, insertions, and actions, students used VR to consider collective functions of muscle groups to describe the actions of someone pitching a baseball. This draws on theoretical knowledge while adding context to their learning.

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MEDICAL IMAGING

Medical imaging provides *in vivo* visualization of anatomical structures, physiology, and pathological processes (Estai & Blunt, 2016). Popular techniques such as computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and ultrasound produce detailed, commonly 2D, images of internal anatomy (Binder et al., 2019; Estai & Blunt, 2016; Smith & Barfoot 2021). Educators may use medical imaging to present clinical experience, anatomical variation, and relation to pathology. The data collected from CT and MRIs can be extremely valuable in creating three-dimensional printed models.

Luetmer et al. (2018) found ultrasound to be a successful way to teach upper limb musculoskeletal anatomy to medical and physical therapy students. The increased exposure to medical imaging of anatomical content in an interprofessional context replicated their future professional workplace sparked by collaborative efforts. Students working in interprofessional teams scored higher than individual scores, suggesting that interprofessional team activities using medical imaging improves understanding, builds team skills, and increases clinical application of anatomy (Bergman et al., 2008; Luetmer et al., 2018).

Kinesiologists frequently integrate medical imaging in training and in professional settings. In fact, ultrasound has been described as the “sport medicine physician’s stethoscope” due to its diagnostic use in clinical practice (McCurdie, 2012). A strong foundation in imaging techniques allows for kinesiologists to accurately diagnose, investigate, and prescribe appropriate treatment of injuries (Bonab et al., 2023). Finnoff (2010) suggested sports medicine students learn basic physics principles of ultrasound, the history of ultrasonic medicine, how to optimize, capture, store, and transfer an ultrasound image. They also learned to describe ultrasonographic appearance of adipose, muscle, tendon, ligament, bone, fascia, vessels, nerve, and cartilage, and generate appropriate reports based on their anatomical findings.

Kinesiologists are expected to be familiar with other imaging modalities such as MRI, radiography, and CT to assess various types of injuries. Depending if the injury is soft-tissue, muscle damage, intra-articular lesions, or bony trauma (McCurdie, 2012), kinesiologists are expected to learn which techniques to use and how to use them depending on how the anatomical structures in question appear. Various studies examined students’ perception of imaging modalities and concluded that it enhanced the quality and efficiency of instruction in anatomy. These results were reflected in higher test scores for students experiencing imaging modalities (Grignon et al., 2016). Overall, exposure of high-quality anatomical images puts their understanding into context, especially the relationships between structure and their function, or lack of function depending on the injury. The incorporation of medical imaging technology facilitates a more interactive and engaging learning environment for kinesiology students.

Bioengineering is a multidisciplinary science, where students tend to have backgrounds in physics, computer science, electrical engineering, or other physical sciences with limited anatomy education. They are required to rapidly gain a thorough understanding of the intricacies of human anatomy and specialist terminology early on (Joyce 2012). Carmichael & Robb (2008) arranged for bioengineering students in the biomedical imaging tract to familiarize themselves with anatomy through dissections and interactive presentations of their dissected cadavers. This was a hands-on approach to directly apply anatomical principles into their biomedical imaging degree, where students are tasked to improve image acquisition systems (image physics), advance image processing in CT scans, MRI, ultrasounds, develop systems for image feature analysis and more. The students felt empowered by the professionalism associated with anatomy education, including accountability for actions, working with others (teamwork), respect for patients (confidentiality), and social responsibility (Swartz, 2006).

THREE-DIMENSIONAL (3D) PRINTING

3D printing produces accurate, customizable and tangible models that enhance visuospatial and 3D understanding of anatomical structures (McMenamin et al., 2014). This has revolutionized anatomical education, particularly for anatomy-heavy specialties like surgery, histopathology, and radiology, as it produces accurate anatomical models to enhance visuospatial and 3D understanding of structures and relationships (McMenamin et al., 2014). These physical models allow students to examine anatomical structures in a tangible form, facilitating hands-on learning and promoting “deep learning”. Furthermore, 3D printed models are customizable and easily reproduced, especially if educators share banks of datasets gathered from CT and MRI scans. The cost for 3D printing varies, with some printers ranging in price from 300 USD to 65,000 USD, and the cost per model ranging from 1.25 USD to 2800 USD (Brumpt et al., 2023). This has made them a popular alternative to traditional cadaveric dissections as they are affordable, reproducible, and cover large ranges of anatomical variations and pathologies that cadavers cannot.

Plastic anatomical models are currently idealized in medical anatomy but do not include the anatomical variations found during cadaveric dissection. Therefore, customized 3D printing models created from real patient data provides tactile experience and variation exposure for anatomy students. These 3D printed variations can be physically manipulated by students and preserved for future generations of students (Fasel et al., 2016; Moore et al., 2018). Surveys show medical students and educators resoundingly attest to the invaluable role of 3D models within the medical curriculum (AbouHashem et al., 2015; Garas et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2018; Young et al., 2019).

3D printed models serve as tangible learning aids for bioengineering students, allowing physical interaction with replicas of complex anatomical structures. This hands-on experience is invaluable for understanding the spatial relationships and intricate

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details of human anatomy that are often difficult to grasp through 2D images or textbooks alone. For example, Bertolini et al. (2021) explains that 3D printing in anatomy education for bioengineers can create accurate educational tools to illustrate complex cardiovascular anatomy and pathology. The 3D rendering guarantees a better understanding of fine anatomical details that may influence the management of disease in comparison to 2D images. As CT scans lead to the creation of whole-organ models through 3D printing, students can even reverse engineer printed models to enhance dimensional accuracy, ensuring digital and physical models match.

In artificial modeling, 3D bioprinting produces mesotissues, microtissues, and organoids to develop human disease models for drug discovery and toxicology. This intricate process requires the bioengineer to be familiar with several factors, such as morphology of anatomical structures, histology, biomaterials, cell biology, physics, engineering, and medicine to accurately select materials based on sensitivities of cell types, growth and differentiation factors, and technical challenges related to tissue being mimicked (Grignon et al., 2016; Morris, 2018). This multidisciplinary nature allows engineers to tackle surgical challenges such as knee joint replacement. By incorporating anatomical principles into computational models, bioengineers can simulate realistic physiological conditions and provide insights into the biomechanical behavior of the knee joint. This approach not only enhances our understanding of joint mechanics but also informs the design of orthopedic implants and rehabilitation strategies. Today's successful bioengineers and anatomists have bioprinted skin, bone, vascular grafts, tracheal splints, heart tissue and cartilaginous structures for surgical transplant (Morris, 2018).

Innovative technology continues to trend across disciplines and such coveted tools tend to enhance spatial understanding and interactivity in anatomical education. However, certain challenges and limitations of these instructional methods suggest a need for renewed emphasis on living anatomical education. A balance of technological tools with anatomy learned through one's physical and self-reflective experience can provide the contextual depth necessary for a balanced, and comprehensive learning environment—a need explored in Discussion.

DISCUSSION: LIVING ANATOMY SUPPLEMENTS THE LIMITATIONS OF MODERN TECHNOLOGICAL APPROACHES

Without doubt, modern technology provides interactive, engaging, and immersive learning experiences, resulting in expeditious advancements in anatomical education globally. However, these instructional tools bring inherent limitations, such as a lack of personal relevance, which can hinder the development of a fully immersive and comprehensive curriculum. One method to address limitations is to supplement technology with experiential learning, such as living anatomy. Examples of living anatomy include live model examinations, palpation, body painting (where deep structures are painted on the surface of the skin), movement, and self-reflection. Movement and self-reflection in learners activate their sensory-motor systems; this in turn consolidates anatomical comprehension, such as recalling structure names, localization, spatial recognition, and function (Cherdieu et al., 2017; Soames & Palastanga, 2019). These experiences offer students a holistic understanding that integrates abstract knowledge from technological tools with the practical, sensory-rich encounters necessary for their future professional roles. By blending technology with living anatomy, educators have an opportunity to create a comprehensive and balanced anatomy curriculum that prepares students for real-world demands.

Common limitations of VR and AR include cost and accessibility, as specialized equipment and yearly subscriptions for software can become costly, and side effects like motion sickness, eye fatigue, disorientation, and discomfort, which negatively impact learning experiences (Chang et al., 2020). Another limitation is the current lack of tactile stimulation, which decreases the face validity – degree to which reality is accurately represented – in anatomy students' immersive learning experience (Baniasadi et al., 2020; Meyer et al., 2021; Vaghela et al., 2021). While haptic feedback is currently being developed for VR and AR, this is presently problematic as anatomy students in medicine, therapy and kinesiology require sufficient face-validity contexts that emulate their future professional settings to ensure preparedness. Furthermore, due to lack of consensus on VR and AR efficacy, future studies should consider focusing on comparing different features of digital-based methods rather than just comparing digital-based to traditional methods. Considering the benefits of improved engagement, learning experiences, repeated use, versatility, the cost-benefit trade-off will vary based on institutional goals and resources.

Medical imaging is extremely useful in teaching anatomical variation, relation to pathology, and diagnostic familiarization through problem solving skills and critical thinking when deducing abstract images (Estai & Blunt, 2016). Similarly, a limitation to medical imaging is the lack of the “feel” of tissue, which is a crucial aspect of learning human anatomy. For professions that must be well-versed in diagnostic ability, anatomy curricula could provide the missing tactile engagement with living anatomy education, such as palpation. Palpation examination is a procedure where a healthcare professional presses a specific region of a patient's body with fingers to detect the presence of features and abnormalities under the skin (Ribeiro et al., 2016). 3D printing has gained traction as a cost-effective alternative to traditional cadaveric dissections as they are affordable, reproducible, and cover a wide range of anatomical variations and pathologies. However, limitations include concerns about color and texture realism compared to living bodies and cadavers (Yuen 2020). While 3D models hold great promise in anatomical curricula, they underscore the need for

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physical interaction with human living anatomy to develop a more nuanced understanding, especially for students preparing for clinical practice.

This integrated approach addresses the sensory limitations of digital tools while connecting theoretical knowledge with one's own living body. For example, therapy and kinesiology students may experience living anatomy to emphasize the interactions between muscles, joints, and bones during movement (Rabattu et al., 2022), spatial orientation, natural variations, and insights to the applied aspects of our dynamic anatomy (Asad et al., 2023). Rabattu et al. (2022) found that kinesiology experimental participants with movement exercises throughout the semester demonstrated significantly higher scores on the final exam compared to the control participants. It was concluded that triggering one's own living body through movement enhances anatomical learning outcomes, especially when integrated into the curriculum deliberately.

Dancers use their experiential anatomical understanding to enhance awareness of their bodies, aiding in injury prevention and expressing authentic emotions through movement (Pengelly 2010). Salk (2005) shares how anatomy education for dancers involves tracing muscle lines, experiencing joint movements, and understanding functionality of joints to develop a comprehensive understanding of their bodies' capabilities and limitations. Concepts like "proximal stability for distal mobility" and "kinetic chains" empower performers to strike a balance between strength, flexibility, and artistic expression to convey narratives effectively, enriching their performances (Rózsavölgyi 2021; Salk 2005; Skotnicka et al., 2017). Experiential anatomy equips dancers with knowledge to make informed choices about their training, thereby promoting longer and healthier performance careers (Pengelly 2010; Rózsavölgyi, 2021; Salk 2005).

Visual artists also benefit from experiential anatomical education, which often includes gesture drawing, sculpting, and digital modeling to effectively study anatomy while catering to different student preferences. For example, life drawing sessions with nude models promote self-reflection and help students understand the body's proportions and muscle structure, while sculpting allows for a tactile exploration of three-dimensional form (Inalouei, 2024).

Living anatomy education in bioengineering has played a pivotal role in developing detailed, customized prosthetics (Bisht et al., 2019). While bioprinting is a powerful tool that precisely places cells, biomaterials, and biomolecules in 3D space to build intricate anatomical structures, such as tissues and organs for organ transplantation, prosthetics, and surgical innovations (Seol et al., 2014), the success of these technologies heavily relies on a deep understanding of living anatomy. Bioprinting involves the technical aspects of printing biocompatible materials and cells and a nuanced comprehension of the functional and structural complexities of living tissues. For example, the design of a novel hand prosthesis by Dunai et al. (2020) underscores the importance of this knowledge. The prosthetic hand, fitted with sensors and actuators to allow motorized fingers to perform grasping movements, was developed with meticulous attention to the human hand's anatomy, including its dimensions, proportions, and functionality. The success of such devices hinges on an accurate replication of living anatomy, as even slight deviations can result in diminished functionality or user discomfort.

While modern technologies have brought significant advancements to anatomy education in spatial understanding and accessibility, their limitations underscore the enduring value of sensory-rich experiences in living anatomy. This is particularly significant in fields that need strong tactile understanding of human tissue, such as therapy, kinesiology, performing arts, and bioengineering. Technology alone cannot fully prepare students for practical, clinical settings. Living anatomy reinforces theoretical understanding, nurtures practical skills, and promotes a deeper understanding of our bodies' structures and functions. This immersive, sensory experience can reinforce the spatial orientation, proprioception, and anatomical variability learned from technological tools. Through exercises such as live model observation, palpation, body painting, self-reflection, and movement analysis, students gain a physical, interactive understanding of anatomical structures that technology cannot currently replace. Therefore, integrating living anatomy with modern technological tools creates a balanced curriculum that bridges the gap between virtual representations and the physical realities of human anatomy.

CONCLUSION

Anatomy is a foundational element across diverse disciplines; many post-secondary programs in therapy, creative and performing arts, kinesiology, and bioengineering programs aim to include some form of anatomical education. This narrative review highlights the successful application of key technological innovations in anatomy education across disciplines, such as 3D visualization software's ability to gain multiple perspectives of challenging anatomical structures, VR and AR's push for interactive spatial learning, medical imaging and its connection to clinical insight, and 3D printing with its strong tactile learning through physical manipulation of structures. While each tool offers unique and specific to its discipline, they also face common limitations such as lack of tactile feedback, high cost, and not fully replicating the face validity of living tissues or professional contexts. This review emphasizes the importance of living anatomy – anatomy learned through experiencing one's own body in real-time through movement and self-reflection – and how its direct sensory-motor engagement can be a vital supplement to these technologies in various disciplines.

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By leveraging the strengths of both innovation and living experiences, educators can create a balanced, comprehensive and dynamic learning experience where students become equipped with foundational theoretical knowledge and practical real-world competencies required in applied settings.

This article addresses a critical gap in the literature by promoting cross-disciplinary collaboration, examining both technological and experiential methods in anatomy education, advocating for an integrative curriculum where instructors can draw from the successes and insights from teaching approaches across various disciplines. For instructors inspired to integrate more anatomy into their curriculum, it is crucial to consider the cost and benefits of each method, align them with course objectives, and determine the most suitable combination of teaching methods to meet their educational goals. This allows anatomical education to become a rich, multidimensional experience as one directly experiences the theoretical concepts on the physical structures and functions of a living body. Learning anatomy intellectually can be useful, but the *felt sense* of one's own body comes through experience, experimentation, and proprioception (Smith 2019).

In recognizing the preferences, successes, and limitations of other disciplines and how they apply modern technological instructional tools, this narrative review sought to address the knowledge gap of how various disciplines teach and apply anatomical concepts specific to their field, paving the way for future interdisciplinary advancements in anatomical research, technological education approaches, and overall practice.

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